

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B142
Date: 29 Nov 2005
Take Off: 11:09:27
Landing: 15:56:35
Flight Time: 4h47m08

Campaign: MICROMIX
Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	3 rd Pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
4	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist	Stuart Newman	Met Office
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Dropsondes / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
10	SWS Training	Dave Kindred	Met Office
11	MARSS/DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	MARSS/DEIMOS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
13	ADA / CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
14	Mission Scientist 2	Clare Lee	Met Office
15	TAFTS	Jon Murray	Imperial College, London
16	TAFTS training	Neil Humpage	Imperial College, London
17	Mission Scientist training	Anthony Baran	Met Office
18	FAAM Obs	Kate Turnbull	Met Office / FAAM
19	SA Obs	Fiona Hilton	Met Office

Flight Track:

B142 Track 29-NOV-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B142
 Date: 29 November 2005
 Project: micromix
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
100459		preflight complete	0.00 kft	228	Horace reboot required. INU u/s
110927		T/O	0.00 kft	000	cranfield
112540		port aft dlu reboot	10.0 kft	000	height and pressure n ow correct
113520		transit climb	10.9 kft	008	to fl 200
115320		FFC & DFC	20.0 kft	359	tape no 1
115603	122214	Profile 1	19.9 - 4.7 kft	132	rate of descent to 50 0ft/min
115728		nev zero	18.7 kft	169	
120001		jw zero	16.3 kft	009	
121849		interrupt p1	1.2 kft	002	1000ft qnh 1007
121950		resume p1	1.2 kft	002	
122226	123227	Run 1	0.19 - 0.20 kft	359	
122552		video	0.20 kft	359	dfc becomes ufc
122805		bbr	0.18 kft	359	retract lower shroud
122943		jw zero	0.21 kft	359	
123227	123420	Profile 2	0.20 - 1.1 kft	035	
123606	124607	Run 2	1.1 kft	359	1000ft
124607	124916	Profile 3	1.1 - 3.1 kft	011	
124753		heiman/bbr	2.2 kft	007	h cal and lower shroud extended during profile
125111		Profile 3 resumed	3.1 kft	015	3000ft
125209	130211	Run 3	3.6 kft	011	end profile 3
125324		heiman/bbr	3.6 kft	000	h to measure lower shroud retracted
125624		video	3.6 kft	359	tape 2 started
130353	131343	Run 4	3.6 kft	359	
130655		ffc demist on	3.6 kft	359	
131539	133029	Profile 4	3.6 - 15.9 kft	359	
131715		heiman/bbr	4.3 kft	359	h cal and lower shroud extended during profile
131950		rate of climb	5.9 kft	000	increased to 1000ft/m in at fl50
133151		descent	15.9 kft	359	positioning for run
133300	134303	Run 5	15.0 kft	359	
133406		ffc obscured	15.0 kft	000	
133430		heiman bbrs	15.0 kft	003	to measure and lower shroud retracted
134401	140113	Profile 5	15.2 - 29.0 kft	359	
134553		ffc	17.0 kft	357	demist overwhelmed
134633		heiman & bbr	17.6 kft	358	cal & extend
134710		video	18.1 kft	000	dfc set
135135		interrupt P5	22.0 kft	077	fl220
135346		resume p5	22.0 kft	253	
135703		ffc	25.2 kft	181	demister overwhelmed, camera obscured
140229		heiman bbr	29.0 kft	112	measure retract
140335	141335	Run 6	29.0 kft	004	
140401		sonde 1	29.0 kft	018	
140544		ffc	29.0 kft	009	set to rfc
141601	142552	Run 7	29.0 kft	359	
141632		sonde 2	29.0 kft	177	
142841	145534	Profile 6	29.0 - 3.5 kft	000	
142947		heiman bbr	27.9 kft	001	cal, extend
145703	150215	Run 8	3.5 kft	115	
145803		heiman bbr	3.5 kft	359	measure retract

155857

Land

0.48 kft

238 EGTC 15:56:35

Trials Instruction for Meteorological Research Flying

Sortie Brief

MICROMIX

Flight: B142

Date: 28 November 2005

Trial Objectives:

To characterise the microphysics of mixed phase cloud and atmospheric state in conjunction with an AMSU overpass for validating radiative transfer models.

Location:

A region of mixed phase cloud anticipated to lie in the South West Approaches which will coincide with an AMSU overpasses at 13:10, 14:05 and 14:13.

Weather:

'Reasonably' homogenous mixed phase cloud.

Flight Pattern:

1. 11:00 Take off Cranfield and transit to operating area at appropriate level (40 mins)
2. 11:40 Profile descent to minimum permitted altitude at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min as necessary (15 min)
3. 11:55 One 10 min SLR at 100 ft (10 min)
4. 12:05 Profile ascent to 1000ft below cloud base (10 min)
5. 12:15 Two SLRs of 10 min each (20 min)
6. 12:35 Profile Ascent to Freezing level (5 min)
7. 12:40 Two SLRs of 10 min each at the freezing level adjusting height as necessary (25 min)
8. 13:05 Profile Ascent to 100 ft above cloud tops (10 min)
9. 13:15 Two SLRs of 10 min each (25 min)
10. 13:40 Profile ascent to max altitude (15 mins)
11. 13:55 Two 10 mins SLRs dropping one sonde at the start of each run (20 min)
12. 14:15 Profile descent to min alt at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min as necessary with 10 min SLRs to be performed at levels within cloud to be determined by the aircraft scientist (85 min)
13. 15:40 One 10 min SLR at 100 ft (10 min)
14. 15:50 Recover to Cranfield (40 min)
15. 16:30 Land Cranfield

Runs and profiles to be conducted at 200 KIAS. Items 6 and 7 should be conducted within cloud as much as possible.

Special note for items 6,7 and 12: During these runs Mission Scientist and Cloud physics operator should monitor cloud physics probes for icing. In the event of icing, 2 min of sideslip oscillations of +/- 5 deg and 20 s period should be introduced into the run for the purposes of turbulence probe testing.

Mission scientist's debrief for flight B142

Stuart Newman

MICROMIX sortie in Southwest Approaches

The general weather situation was a warm front heading south-eastwards bringing low and mid-level cloud down across Ireland. Aims of the sortie were to sample the microphysics of mixed-phase cloud as well as measure microwave radiation below and above the cloud in conjunction with satellite overpasses.

Take-off was at 110855, with transit via the Daventry corridor at FL100. An ascent to FL200 was followed by a profile descent to 50 feet close to the northern edge of the Irish FIR boundary. Approximate cloud tops were found to be at FL185, but this was a relatively thin layer of altostratus with clear air below. From around FL100 downwards (but variable spatially) a more substantial layer of cloud was encountered, with a mix of graupel and snow down to the freezing level at 3000-3500 feet. Large water droplets were detected in the lowest cloud layers, and below the cloud base at approx. 1000-1500 feet it was raining. A run at 100 feet was followed by ascent to 1000 feet for a second run, the northern end of which entered cloud base. A further ascent and runs at 3500 feet enabled the freezing layer to be well sampled (big irregular particles seen on CPI as well as few smaller hexagonal columns, also some snow-like particles and droplets seen on 2D probes). An ascent to FL150 allowed a run in between cloud layers in clear air at the beginning, in cloud at the end. A profile ascent (just out of cloud at FL165) terminated at FL290 to fit in with satellite overpass times; two runs were performed with a sonde dropped at the beginning of each. Also some interesting intermittent contrailing conditions were found at this level, with some captured on the rear-facing video camera. Halos (concentric rings) were seen below the aircraft indicating ice cloud optical phenomena.

Time constraints meant that only a profile descent and a run at the freezing level around 3500 feet were possible for the latter part of the sortie. Cloud tops were around FL146 (in clearance again at FL130) and by FL100 large snow and smaller particles were detected. At the freezing level the 2D probes picked up 60-65% non-spherical particles; the CPI was non-operational for this run, and the CIP probe was showing long-running problems. Transiting back to Cranfield, the aircraft landed at 1559. Flight duration 4 hrs 50 mins.

Summary:

A good MICROMIX sortie, successfully probing mixed-phase cloud in association with MARSS and satellite microwave measurements.

Instruments:

The INU was not working for this flight, so wind and heading information was lacking; the cruciform GPS was, however, working.

TAFTS had problems with laser fringes again.

Deimos data appeared to be gibberish, will need later analysis; all MARSS channels worked however.

CPI generally worked well, but shut down for final straight and level run.

SWS was operated, but only as a training flight.

FWVS was switched on but data looked extremely suspect.

General Eastern humidity showed large oscillations at times.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEUMAN

Flight No **B.142**.....

Date **29/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110855					TAKE OFF
1120		FL100			Transit via Darenty Corridor to SW Approaches / South of Ireland
					INU not working, so some parameters not available.
1133		FL100			within cloud
1134					Climb to FL200 prior to descent
					TWC expected to be offscale as recently refilled; FWS not working.
1140		FL200			Bristol Channel area.
					Missy Sc below. Few wispy Ci above
					79.2 } Engine settings 80.5 } In and out of contrailing 83.2 } 4.7 }
115603	P1	FL200↓		SI.5N 4.5W	
1158		FL185			Approx. cloud top at our level
1200		FL163		SI.4 4.9	In clearance between cloud layers
1201					Cu/Sc below and above
1208		~7000ft			Mix of graupel and snow shaped
1211		FL050		SI.4 N 6.05W	Tops of Cu ~ 5000ft slowing descent to 500ft/min
1214		4000ft			~ -1.5°C, approaching freezing level
1215		3000ft			Freezing level ~3000ft on 2D-P, wet snow-like particles
					Occasionally out of cloud, not very substantial cloud
1217		1700'			Raining

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.14.2**

 Date **29/11/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1218		1000'			Interruption to probe just visual with surface
1220					Large water droplets ~ 400µm in lowest parts of cloud
1222/14	end profile				
1222/26	R1	100 ft			
1224		"			In precipitation (rain) T ~ 6°C, TD ~ 5-7°C
1227		"			Clearing much of the precipitation
1228		"			27kt, 7kn wind (flight deck console)
1230		"		50.8 N 6.6 W	T (air) ~ 6.5°C, T (dew) ~ 5°C
1232/27	end R1				
1232/27	P2				Profile to 1000 feet
1234/10	end P2	1000'		50.7 N 6.5 W	Manoeuvring for run
1236/06	Run 2	"			~ 4.5°C (dew 3°C) Raining.
					Wind westerly at 16-20 knots below cloud base, but deepening all the time at northern end of Run
1239		~1025 feet		50.9 -6.6	
1242		"			Just in base of cloud beams of water droplets backed up by FSSP
1246/07	end R2 start P3	1000' ↑		51.2	In cloud at end of run, fairly heavy precipitation
					Concs ↑, size ↓ ~ 400µm during profile on 2D probes
	end profile	3000 ft			
					Resumption of profile climb to 3500 ft to be in mixed layer
1251					Ice seen at 3100-3200 ft
1252/09	end prof start run	3500 ft			Large particles on 2D P (snow?) 2D-C smaller (graupel)
		"			concs 2000 counts/m ³ 2D-P 63 " " 2D-C
1254	R3	"			Big irregular particles on CPI, few smaller hexagonal

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.42**.....

 Date **29/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1256		3500'			Columns on 2D-P(?) Not confirmed by CPI, hexagonal plates
1259		"		50.9 -6.6	Rounded, sph - mixed phase (2D-P) mostly droplets on CPI
1301		"			Some ice formed on unused canisters, not yet seen on other probes
1302					Few angular particles on both CPI and 2D-P
130211	end R3				↑ also columns
					out of cloud at end of Run, few Cu below
130353	start R4				-0.6°C air, 0.2°C dew
1306		3500'		51N 6.6E	-0.8°C air, -0.05 dew
1307					2D-C 50 count / litre 2D-P 4.5 " "
1309		"			On flight deck radar can see cellular pattern to liquid water ahead.
1311		"		51.3N 6.6E	Aggregates, snow, droplets on 2D-P, CPI not too useful Similar story from CPI
131343	end R4	"			
131549	P4	3500' ↑		51.4N -6.6E	Climb to approx. FL160 Not thick cloud, visibility improves in patches to cloud below.
					Rate of climb increased from 500 ft/min to 1000 ft/min at FL150
1321	"				In thick-ish cloud, by eye, though Tair ~ -7.3 Tdew -4.6 so some calibration offset it seems
1328					In clearance between lower level cloud and higher, thinner CuSc.
133029	end P4				Ending profile at FL160

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.142**.....

 Date **29/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133130		FL150 ↓ FL150			Adjusting to FL150 to drop below cloud at ~FL156
133300	R5	FL150		50.2 -6.5 50.5 -6.5	Still in clearance but thicker cloud ahead on this heading Fairly homogeneous cloud below by eye Big aggregates in thin cloud encountered on this run at northern end
1338				7.77 62 82 4.9	← N1 ← TGT (contains again (engine settings) ← N2 ← FF/FU)
"					Entering thicker cloud ISA-5 concs ↑ ~2000 counts/m ³ -19.8°C air, -16.2°C dew
1342					CPI: dendrites, hexagonal columns now too
134303	end R5	FL150			Starting climb
134401	P5	FL150 FL290 FL165			Just out of cloud Fluffy tops below, Sc-looking
1348		FL180			Nothing on 2D probes, in clear air
135135	interm. P5	FL220			Interrupted profile, still in clear Some elevated cloud tops from convection presumably, the Sc in appearance
135346	resume P5	FL220↑ FL250			In climb, Tair ~ -39°C, Tdew ~ -41°C
1356				95 75 91 6.7	} no contrails
140113	end P5	FL290			Few breaks in cloud below
140335	Start R6	FL290			Sonde released at start of run 356° 80 knots wind on release
140430				86.0 67 86 4.7	} Contrailing now on and off intermittent

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.142**.....

 Date **29.11.05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					"Spectacular" contrails
140930					83.8 } engine settings 64 } 84.9 } 4.3 } ↑ 430 kg/hr fuel flow
					447 } fuel flows 440 } 445 } 449 } at 141130
					Contrails gone at 1412 back at 1413
141552	start R7	FL290			sonde released successfully
141601					good video of sonde going, still contrailing.
					84.7 } engines 64.9 } 85.4 } 4.5 }
		FL290			-49°C air -50.5°C dew
					7000' above us contrailing aircraft, we are top at 1424 intermittent
					84.7 } we are 64.9 } contrailing 85.4 } 4.5 }
142552	end R7	FL290			manoeuvring to position for probe
142841	start P6	FL290 ↓		50.4 -6.2	descent at 1000' / min to 3500 feet (freezing level)
1443		FL155			Halo forward / starboard down below, concentric rings
144030		FL146			Entering cloud top
					56.2 } Contrails, smaller 64.9 } than before 76.9 } 3.3 }
					Fuel flow 1330 across all engines

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2.

Flight No **B.142**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110855			INU not working		T10. At start of flight height + pres were not reading
112800		FL100			Back on ok. N.B. INU U/S, have GPS Guaciform instead.
113451					Climbing to FL200
114200				GPS not INU	FWUS being switched on. TWC needs post calibration.
115018		FL200	51.6N 51.6N, 3.9E		Contacting wispy stopped.
115200					
115603	P1	FL200			Profile descent to FL50 near 818 W. → 18 W.
121130			1000ft		Changing rate of descent from 1000ft/min to 500ft/min.
121558					2D mixture of drops + snow. 2DP seeing max 300µm.
121726		FL18			2D seeing all water drops.
121850	Plnt.	1000ft			Intercept to new heading to be on cross wind.
121952	Pl st.	1000ft.			2DC seeing 400µm dia. water drops.
1220					below cloud.
1220	Pl end	to 50ft			
122214	R1st.	100ft.			below cloud. Rear camera looks clear, forward looks ^{semi} opaque

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2

Flight No **B**.....142.....
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
122827				50.9, -6.7	wind 276°, 7kts.
122928					seeing some precip. 2D + VFC seeing
123227	Rend P2st	1000ft. 1000ft.		50.79, -6.52	Climb to 1000ft.
123420	Rend R2st	1000ft.			1010 mb. ⇒ FL ⇒ 1000 ⇒ 1050ft. right turn.
123606	R2st	1000ft.			2D not seeing anything yet. 16kts
124200					Pilot called in dwd base 2D seeing v. small values. 1 ⇒ 7 conts / litre water drops.
124348				51.15, -6.71	Higher concs: water drops.
124607	R2end P3st	1000ft. 1000ft.			Higher precip. also seeing dwd below. Profiling to 3000ft.
124712		1700ft.			2D concs. shot up. drop size 400µm.
124836		2700ft.			small sizes. + mixture.
1249	P3end	3000ft.			water + snow from 2D.
125111	P3st.				2D CPL now seeing ice.
125219	P3end R3st	3500ft. 3500ft.			T - 0.71C, TD - 0.56C
					2DP snow, 2DC graupel. 2000 conts 1L ³

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2.

Flight No **B142**.....

Date **29/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CPI seeing large particles. mainly hexagonal.
125624					2D seeing columns. CPI only seeing hexagonal plates. not seeing water drops
125917				50.9, -6.6	FSSP strobing + 2D showing more spherical \rightarrow mixed phase.
130149					2D seeing irregular shapes. CPI mainly columns
130211	R3 _{end}	3500ft.		50.74, -6.56	
130353	R3 R4	3500ft.		50.76, -6.53	Reciprocal run. 2D irregular shapes 2DC 50 counts/l 2DP 4.5 counts/l CPI100 taking images. $T_D = 0.26^\circ$, $T = 0.07^\circ\text{C}$
131004					DFC can see patchy sea. ~ 4/8. still in cloud though. 2D seeing aggregates, snow, some drop, columns. 2DP large particles. CPI quite large aggregates.
131343	R4	3500ft.		51.37, -6.58	end of run.
131539	P4	3500ft.			Present
	RS	15000ft.			Run between 2 layers.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2.

Flight No **B.42**.....
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133850		15000ft			Con trailing
133919					Stopped con trailing
133946					Con trailing again. very variable
134025				50.74, 6.44	2D seeing values celesting up. 2000 units 1L ³ 2DP CPL seeing some large hexagonal cels.
134303	R5 end				
134401	PS st	FL 2000 FL 150		50.9, -6.39	to FL 290
134646					FINVS VIS being investigated. all OK. no working. O3 reading 40.9 ppb. on Horace reading -0.5 ppb.
135135	PS int	FL 220		50.9, -6.25	Leading to max alt.
135346	PS st	FL 220			climbing. some traffic in the way
14:01:13	PS end	FL 290		50.5, -6.07	N. Athly leading 12 mile drift. turning right.
14:03:35	R6 st	FL 290			Run at max alt.
14:04:01	S1			50.49, -6.24	Drop sander 1. wind at launch. 356°, 80knts. OK. except for wind (not enough satellites).
14:09:12		FL 290		50.86, -6.28	thick contrails.
14:10:30					ARRPS now getting wind data.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:12:15					No contrails.
14:12:30					And back again. (thick again)
14:13:35	R6 end	FL290			end of run. right hand turn. still contrailing
14:15:52	R7 st.	FL290			
14:16:32	S2.	FL290.		50.99, -6.12	Slide 2. release. winds 67 knts. on release.
14:25:52	R7 end	FL290		49.99, -6.03	right turn at end run.
14:28:41	P6 st.	FL290		49.97, -6.2	desert
		FL142			T = -46.52°; T _D = -50.6° In cloud top?
					N.B. Above cloud could see ^{glories} cloud on top of cloud. (multiple - rings)
14:46:11		FL135	360° magnetic 355° true		contrailing on right side
14:48					2D seeing some large snow. then v. small stuff.
14:50:13					getting slightly larger. ~ 200µm 2DP T & T _D ~ -5 ~ 600µm 1L 2D 1100µm 1L 2D
14:54:30		5000ft.			2DP seeing drops.
14:55:34	P6 end	3500ft.			right hand turn.
14:57:03	R8 st.	3500ft.			run in mixed phase.
14:58:36					SID. seeing 61% nonspherical ⇒ mixed phase.
15:02:50	R8 end	3500ft.			Final run end, left hand turn + transit back.

15:59:00 Landing

~ 3hrs science
~ 4hr 52min duration.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Fiana Hulme

Flight No B.142.....

Date 29/11/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.33					in cloud W.5km
					can still just about see the ground
11.35					climbing to F200
11.36.39					Above thin patchy cloud (& snow!)
11.38.00					clearish again
11.43.00					just beginning to fly over patchy cloud
11.50.					contracts
11.51.21					Passing over the coast now
11.55.06					come out of clear patch, now
					small cumulus clouds below
11.56.03	P1				profile descent from F200
11.56.03					
12.00.07		15400			cumulus below, thin cloud above now
12.06.21		9900			entering cloud
12.11.51		4700			cloud thinning out below - we
					seem to be a bit inbetween 2
					layers of cloud. Top layer extensive
12.14.00		3500			cloud patchy below, solid above
12.15.36		2700			into lower cloud layer
12.17.56		1600			exiting below cloud just about
12.18.50		1000			interruption to profile to turn
					P
12.19.50					recommence profile.
					Below main cloud but still
					very wet - ZDC still shows
					particles.

12.22.14 End

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Fiona Hulton

Flight No **B.142**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12.51.00	P3				To 3500
12.52.00	P3	3500			
12.53.00					2D - snow + graupel 2000 / 100 ^{63/100}
					CPI - big particles hexagonal hexagonal
12.54.00		3500			cloud below - gaps, above - complete cover
12.56.31					2D - needle/column?
					CPI - hexagonal plates
12.59.15					droplets / mixed phase
13.00.00					dewpoint has separated some way
13.01.49					2D more angular particles CPI columns
13.02.11	End	3500			Gaps in cloud below
13.03.53	P4	3500			Flying above small cumulus w/ stratus ^(?) above
13.06.19					looking more foggy now at our level. C50 / L P4.5 / L
13.09.24					Dewpoint back same as T100 cloud still has gaps below.
13.11.45					snow, droplets, aggregates 2D CPI quite big clumps
13.13.43	End	3500			
13.15.39	P4	3500			→ max altitude.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Fiona Hutton

Flight No **B.142**.....

Date 29/11/05.....

Page 4 of 6...

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.35.30	P4	15000			contrails
					Flying between two cloud layers hard to tell when contrails are ^{because of} the ^{the} is ^{is}
13.40.40	P5				2000 / m ³ 2DP counts well up Dewpoint well away ~4K warmer than T CPI dendritic hexagonal.
13.43.05	P5end	15000			
13.44.01	P5	15000			to FL300-ish
13.45.23		~16000			coming out of cloud top
13.49.22		20100			still flying above complete cloud cover
13.51.36	end	F2200K			Interrupt profile
13.53.46	restart	F220			resume
13.57.54		26000			clear skies, no contrails
14.01.13	P5end	29000			
14.03	P6	FL290			
14.04.00					sonde dropped
14.04.35					contrails - big but gone quickly!
14.04.47					no contrails
14.08.50					storming contrails, really big
14.10.42					contrails dissipating slightly
14.11.52					contrails stopped
14.12.30					good contrails again

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Fiona Hilton

Flight No **B.142**.....
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Date **29/11/05**.....

Page **5** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14.13.35	R6 END	29000			
14.16.01	R7	29000			Still flying over alto cumulus type cloud, still excellent contrails
14.16.32					Sonde dropped wind 6 knots
14.20.20					contrails dissipating a bit
14.20.54		29000			no contrails now
14.23.30					no contrails for us one 5000 ft above, behind, contrailing
14.24.44		29000			1000ft up to left contrailing one also to left, lower, smaller cutting across our back <u>not</u> really contrailing; still none for us
14.25.53	END	29000			turning for profile descent
14.28.33					plane to left quite a way off contrailing
14.28.41	P6	29000			descent to 3500
14.44.24					Entering 1st cloud layer Dew Pt -11.36 T -17.65
14.45.30		13300			small contrails again flying between cloud layers
14.46.00		13000			gone again! 'reasonably' homogeneous cloud above and below
14.48.30		10600			at first then 20 large small also small stuff
14.49.00		10000			Flying through lower cloud layers now

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Anthony Baran

Flight No **B.141**
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Date **29/4**

Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1104	TO				
1138		10kft			-10°C - cloud 10kft DENDRITIC - Colloid spheres 0.8µm - 16°C needles Res. EVALUATIONS - DENDRITIC ~ 1000µm ² PLATES Thin PLATES: Aggregates of needles
1206	-9°C	9kft			DENDRITIC - PLATES Layered Plate WATER/ICE
1211	-4°C	5kft			water Plate
1217					Sol ⁿ water Plate
1233		5kft			water spheres possibly SEA spray? - Respiratory aggregates - Detecting 10 ² to 10 ⁴ per water Plate
1227	5kft 5kft				water Plate
1232	knobs under leg				to 10kft
1235	set Alt to 3kft				water spheres
1240	4°C	10kft			water Plate - P
1241	cloud base				cloud / water Plate
1244	start of line to cloud base	3kft			cloud / water Plate
					Respiratory aggregates? Microbial Heavy respiratory - other

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** ¹⁴¹
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 Date 28/11

 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1245	END OF RUN			Winds to 3 left	WATER AT 1500ft
1249	END OF RUN				WATER AT 3000ft to the right
1251	Run to 3000ft				= Aggregates the size of small gravel and large irregular ~17-20 μ matrix + small at base winds 1254
				1256	15 μ dark large platelets
				1258	Small gravel objects 27 μ dark mostly red blue
				102	columns very fine some aggregated in region ~30 μ
1030pm	Aggregates Run				
1040pm					noisy and platelets with large irregular platelets ~40 μ
1140pm					Mixture of Aggs + aggregates ~20 μ (dark)
					Mixture of Aggs + Aggs and aggregates: - dark V-type
Run 4	ended at 1:15pm				
1:15pm	1:15pm				

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	29/11/05	Flight	B142	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard/Harlow		Campaign	MICROMIX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start MARSS

Visual pod inspection						
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58 °C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time 08:55					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					09:00
Scan indication	Monitor			x	Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					09:30
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						X
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual	
Weather	Cloud	Ci and med 2/8	Precip	No		
	Surface	Yes	Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$					at time
Brightness temps 'sensible'						X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.56	Cold	278.62	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	43.82	35.04	38.29	37.88	41.17	

Power changeover

Headset on before start					
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again	at time				
	10:58:40				

Flight #	B142	Date	29/11/05	Operator(s)	Pollard/Harlow	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
10:58:51			Power c/o: only lost deimos computer Marss all working ok, Deimos quicklook data is gibberish.						
11:08			Take off: MARSS still working properly						
11:24:41			Time stamp check!						
11:30:42			Laptop time 25s behind DRS						
11:32:04			Fixed it now, laptop time synced to DRS						
11:38:00			Climbed to FL200 just passed over a sheet of St						
11:41:43		FL200	At FL 200, Zen BTs all low						
11:47:09			Looks pretty clear above, 7/8 Cu/Sc below						
11:53:39			Small amounts of thin cloud just below our current level, 4/8 Sc below						
11:55:51	P1	FL200	Profile descent						
12:07:32			In cloud						
12:09:35			2D and CPI seeing graupel and large 'snowflakes', odd column						
12:11:31			In a clear slot below main bulk and in tops of underlying convection						
			Ch 16 and 17 showing structure aloft dring descent.						
12:17:21			2D reporting water						
12:17:49			Bobbling along in base of convection						
12:18:47	P1		Interrupt						
12:19:47	P1		Recommenced 400micron water on 2d						
12:22:12	P1	50ft							
12:22:27	R1	100ft	Under cloud						
12:24:31			In precip, drifting out						
12:26:29			16, 17 and to a lesser extent 20, showing periodic variability						
12:27:16			Small amount of precip						
			16, 17 and 20 indicate cloud thinning above						
12:28:38			16,17,20 sharp inc in BTs, returning to pevious values						
12:32:23	R1		End						
	P2	100ft	Start						
12:34:16	P2	1000ft	End of run, turning into wind onto reciprocal						
			Not in bases						
12:36:04	R2	1000ft	Started out of cloud, bases not far above						
12:40:19			Just had a spike in 16,17 and 20, seems to coincide with a feature from previous run. Coming level with base.						
12:45:16			Fairly heavy precip coincident with sharp nc in 16and 17 BTs						
12:46:05	R2	1000ft	End						
	P3		Start to 3000ft						
			2D large inc in concentrations, smaller drops approx 400 microns						
12:49:11	P3	3000ft	End, turning on recip						
			2D seeing small drops						

Flight #	B142	Date	29/11/05	Operator(s)	Pollard/Harlow	log page	3	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
12:52:07	R3	3500ft	Start of run, its snowing! Confirmed by CPI						
12:59:51			2D maybe seeing supercooled liquid, increase in 16 and 17 BTs						
13:00:45			Icing on canisters						
13:01:46			2D and CPI getting angular ptles						
13:02:07	R3	3500ft	End of run turn to recip.						
13:03:40	R4	3500ft	Start						
13:11:39			2D showing lots of different stuff, CPI, big aggregates and drops						
13:13:40	R4	3500ft	End, turn on recip.						
13:15:27	P4	3500ft	Start to FL160 @ 500 ft/min initially						
13:30:29	P4	FL150							
13:32:57	R5		Run in between cloud levels, pretty solid above and below						
13:37:44			CPI and 2D big aggregates						
13:40:43			2D, big inc in conc 2k/l						
13:43:03	R5	FL150							
13:43:47	P5								
13:45:20			Out of tops						
13:51:16	P5	FL220	Interrupt						
13:53:46	P5	FL220	Resumed						
14:01:10	P5	FL290	End						
14:03:31	R6	FL290	Start						
14:03:56			Sonde 1						
14:13:32	R6	FL290	End						
14:15:51	R7	FL290	Start						
14:16:29			Sonde 2						
14:25:50	R7	FL290	End						
14:28:38	P6	FL290	Start						
14:43:57			Passing FL150, no cloud above						
14:44:32			Into tops, drop in ch 16 BTs						
14:45:25			Into gap between layers (lower than last time)						
			Seems 'reasonably homogeneous above and below.						
14:48:17			Just coming in tops of bottom layer 2D snow then small stuff.						
14:54:04			2D lookin glike we're coming into water						
			During this profile ch 16 did an interesting 'dog leg' wrt trends in other channels.						
14:55:29	P6	FL035	End						
14:57:01	R8	FL035	Start						
14:59:54			2D appox 60% of ptles non-spherical: mixed phase						
15:02:09	R8	FL035	End of run						
			End of science						

day.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 142	Date	29/11/05		Operator(s)	JR / DEC (V/T)		log page	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks				
				Vis	NIR					

(FW: APT)
+60

Wx, inst. condⁿ.

110924							T/O Crawfield (Bear View)				
							1000m max. Integ ⁿ time				
							NIL.				
133640	S	150	↑	100	500	Dark Current cal ⁿ	Integ ⁿ time		staying same.		
133700							Temp +15.				
134010	}					←	Mirror moved zenith to nadir				
134030											
4215			↓				Start into time				
4250	Change to		↓	150	750		→ Start Dark Current View				
4306							End Dark " "				
							Temp +14				
4325	End.						End Run.				
134401	PS		↓				Prof. 150 ↑ 270 Temp +14.				
134526							Closest Tops 165				
134545	PS ↑	170	↓	150	750		Low Sat. started so change Integ ⁿ time				
134634	PS ↑	175 ↑	↓	100	500		Restart measurement at FL 175.				
135022							Temp +13				
135135	PS		↓	100	500		Interrupt Prof ↑ 220 turn ↓				
135356	PS ↑	220	↓	100	500		Recommence PS.				
135501	PS ↑		↓	75	400		Change Integ ⁿ time (set ⁿ)				
135525											
135800							Change nad → zenith view				
" 35	PS		↑	350	1000		then change Integ ⁿ time.				
135930	End PS	290	↑	"	"		Temp 12				
-							Start Sunde Drop Run Good Temp data				
-							Drop Sunde #1				
140600							Turn zenith to nadir.				
140815	Res.	290	↓	100	500		Reinitialize Good Wind data				
141240		290	↓	100	500		Temp 11 °C. 3 min to Sunde drop #2				

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 142**

Date: 29th November 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	n	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JO1D	N	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	Y
CO	N	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B142

Date: 29th November 2005

Instruments

1. INU – failed to initialise correctly. Did not recover
2. TWC – fitted – serviceable needs calibration
3. HORACE – FWVS raw data reading 65535.
4. Upper camera window – needs to be cleaned – demister is overwhelmed by icing
5. Printer – could not print satcom messages from HORACE terminal except via IE
6. Neph Rack Laptop opens HORACE network but does not plot data

Other Instruments' status

AVAPS – 2 Sondes launched, no problems

ARIES – not operated

SWS, MARSS, ADA, FWVS – Okay

DEIMOS – ok

Cloud Physics – Okay

CPI errors on last run

TAFTS – 'partly working'

SATCOM – messages from dfl ops delayed. From FAAM no delay.

Aircraft

Cabin became rather warm but cooled on request

Satcom H Calls – 1 by DFL

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B142:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
Cloud Physics In Flight	No log is available.
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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